

Chinese Influence in the BRICS+ De-dollarization Process

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Abstract

Since the end of the Second World War, the U.S. dollar has consolidated its position as the main currency of international trade and as a central instrument of power within the International Monetary and Financial System. In this context, debates on de-dollarization have emerged among BRICS countries as an attempt to reduce dependence on the dollar and challenge the power structure historically shaped by the United States. Thus, this article analyzes the influence of Chinese foreign policy on the BRICS+ de-dollarization agenda, focusing on the role of the internationalization of the renminbi. The study seeks to answer the following research question: how does the internationalization of the renminbi, as an instrument of Chinese foreign policy, influence the debate and initiatives of de-dollarization within BRICS? To address this question, the research adopts a qualitative approach based on a critical perspective of International Political Economy and the power relations that structure the International Monetary System, using a deductive method. The findings indicate that although BRICS members share a common political interest in reducing dependence on the U.S. dollar, the de-dollarization process reflects internal disputes and different national interests. In this context, China emerges as a central actor in shaping the debate by promoting the internationalization of the renminbi and encouraging its use in intra-bloc trade. Through strategies such as the creation of alternative payment systems, the strengthening of economic partnerships with the Global South, and the expansion of BRICS+, China seeks to expand its monetary influence.

Keywords: BRICS de-dollarization; Chinese influence; Renminbi internationalization.

Introduction

During the period following the Second World War, the U.S. dollar became widely used in international trade as the standard currency to mediate commercial and financial exchanges between countries. This occurred due to its high liquidity in the context of post-war economic reconstruction. From that moment on, the U.S. currency gradually became integrated into the foreign policy of the United States, functioning as an instrument for the expansion and consolidation of its hegemony in the international system (Fiori, 2012).

The strong dollar policy implemented during the 1990s reinforced the U.S. perspective of using the currency as a tool of power capable of controlling international trade flows and constraining the behavior of other states through economic blockades, reserve freezes, and trade sanctions (Fiori; Tavares, 1998). In this context, the structural power of the United States was consolidated, granting the country a privileged position that allowed it to influence the dynamics of the global economy and its institutions, as well as the existing power structure of the capitalist system (Strange, 1998).

In this context, the debate on de-dollarization among BRICS+ member countries emerges, as the power relations historically constructed by the United States have placed peripheral economies in positions of subordination, dependence, and limited development. In response, de-dollarization is approached by the group as an alternative to reduce dependence on the dollar and the restrictive power structure imposed on the Global South, serving as a political instrument to restructure the International Monetary and Financial System (Liu, 2025).

Among the de-dollarization initiatives discussed by BRICS+ countries, the promotion of local currencies in trade transactions appears as one of the most viable alternatives to reduce dependence on the dollar. However, due to China's strong influence in the bloc's internal discussions on this issue, the process may also reflect a dispute of interests among its members. In this context, despite the shared objective of reducing dependence on the dollar, China may use this scenario to promote its own interests by encouraging the use of the renminbi in transactions between member states and expanding the role of the Chinese currency in the international financial system.

Thus, the main objective of this research is to analyze the participation and influence of Chinese foreign policy in the BRICS de-dollarization project, critically examining the internationalization of the renminbi as a means of strengthening China's economic influence within the bloc. Using a qualitative methodology based on a critical perspective of the power relations within the International Monetary System and applying a deductive method, this study seeks to answer the following research question: How does the internationalization of the renminbi, as an instrument of Chinese foreign policy, influence the debate and initiatives of de-dollarization within BRICS+?

To understand this scenario, the research is divided into two main sections. The first analyzes

China's influence on the internal BRICS+ discussions regarding de-dollarization, while the second investigates the strengthening of the renminbi as part of Chinese foreign policy in the bloc's de-dollarization process.

The Chinese Influence on the BRICS+ De-Dollarization Process

Currency represents an important economic instrument in the dynamics of international relations, reflecting a historical process of construction of the global power structure within the capitalist system. In this context, currency does not function only as a financial asset, but also as a political tool capable of influencing and shaping international trade and economic relations. Therefore, currency is directly associated with the concept of power within the capitalist system, since its control and use can generate strategic advantages for certain states (Fiori; Tavares, 1998).

In this sense, the International Monetary System has historically been structured as a space of power competition among states. The structure of monetary relations between states is therefore consolidated within a power structure characteristic of global capitalism, which tends to privilege core countries while subordinating peripheral economies to a dynamic of structural dependence (Cohen, 2014). In this context, monetary diplomacy represents a sensitive element in international relations, as it may function both as an instrument of competition and as a form of coercion between states seeking to reaffirm or reconfigure the existing monetary order (Metri, 2023).

Thus, the implementation or replacement of a monetary order represents a political decision that reflects the structure of interstate power. In this context, the narrative of de-dollarization promoted by BRICS reaffirms the bloc's political position of contesting the current configuration of international monetary relations, while also questioning the global power structure historically imposed on the Global South as a space of resource extraction and subordination to the interests of central economies.

Although BRICS member states share a political position regarding the need to promote de-dollarization in their intra-bloc trade relations to mitigate the power structure historically imposed by the U.S.-led liberal order, the members diverge regarding which alternative currency should be used in this process. Since currency itself represents a field of competition, the representatives of the bloc have not reached a consensus on an alternative currency, as such a decision could increase the power capacity of the state issuing the dominant currency used in intra-bloc trade.

Thus, the official narrative defended by the bloc regarding the promotion of local currencies in regional BRICS trade may be compromised due to internal disputes over the currency with the greatest potential to be used in the de-dollarization process. In this context, the Chinese

currency becomes a central point of attention in this debate, since China has a certain level of influence in guiding and encouraging internal discussions on de-dollarization. At the same time, its currency represents a strong alternative for the bloc due to China's geopolitical and economic capacity to challenge the dominance of the U.S. dollar (Gurcan, 2019).

The research considers that the current configuration of power in the first quarter of the twenty-first century reflects a dispute between power centers in a possible process of hegemonic transition, from a system centered on the power relations constructed by the United States toward a multipolar organization increasingly influenced by China's political and economic power. Within the intrinsic dynamics of global capitalism, China also views the monetary field as an important arena of competition for expanding its influence in the international system (Hasan, 2026).

In this context, a competition of power between the dollar and the renminbi becomes evident, reflecting China's attempt to reconfigure the International Monetary System through BRICS+. This process occurs through the strengthening of internal debates about the need for de-dollarization, China's role in supporting the expansion of the bloc, and the promotion of the renminbi as an alternative currency to reduce dependence on the dollar in intra-bloc trade. Therefore, this dynamic suggests an attempt to construct a new power relationship in the monetary field that reflects Chinese interests within the bloc.

China may promote a reconfiguration of the monetary order through the internationalization of the renminbi by expanding its use in strategic sectors such as energy and rare minerals, areas in which the country has strong productive and commercial participation (Metri, 2023). In this context, linking these economic sectors to the Chinese currency may encourage other member states to adopt it in their international transactions, strengthening China's economic influence in the international monetary system.

However, reducing the centrality of the dollar does not necessarily mean eliminating monetary dependence within the international system. If this process results in the concentration of monetary power around the renminbi within the bloc's economic relations, states may remain within a structure of dependence on a dominant currency, shifting the monetary axis of power from Washington to Beijing.

Thus, the lack of consensus on this issue remains present in the internal debates among bloc members in their effort to reduce dependence on the U.S. dollar and its associated power structure. Nevertheless, it is possible to highlight China's capacity for influence and its strategic interest in shaping the internal debate on BRICS de-dollarization to increase its monetary power and reconfigure the dynamics of the International Financial System.

The Renminbi Internationalization Strategies and BRICS De-Dollarization

Considering that BRICS constitutes a non-institutionalized platform of multilateral cooperation, some of the issues discussed internally reflect both cooperation and competition among its members, due to the absence of formalized rules and institutional regimes. In the monetary field, the debate on de-dollarization also reflects this competitive environment, in which the main driving force of the project lies in strengthening the renminbi in regional trade among member countries.

The current context of the second decade of the twenty-first century, marked by the gradual decline of United States hegemony and the continued use of the dollar as an instrument of power, a process known as dollar weaponization, creates favorable conditions for the expansion of Chinese influence in global economic and political relations (Hasan, 2026). This movement is particularly relevant in the Global South, which for decades has been within the sphere of influence of the U.S.-led liberal order, often reinforcing its structural dependence. Furthermore, the recent war between Russia and Ukraine, as well as geopolitical tensions between the United States and China, have intensified this debate within the bloc, which is viewed as a way to consolidate strategies capable of mitigating the effects of dependence on the dollar and its use as an instrument of political pressure against BRICS+ countries.

Thus, although it is not formally recorded in official documents and statements of the group, the internationalization and strengthening of the renminbi represent part of the bloc's de-dollarization strategy (Hasan, 2026). In this sense, the initial perspective of encouraging the use of local currencies in intra-bloc trade as the main political strategy for de-dollarization becomes weaker as commercial and financial relations in renminbi intensify. However, this new configuration of power that has been gradually formed within the bloc does not eliminate the growth and encouragement of other member states currencies in this trade, but rather highlights the renminbi and Chinese foreign policy as the main actors in this process.

Russia, for example, has increasingly used the renminbi as an alternative way to circumvent economic and political sanctions imposed by Washington. For other countries in the bloc, strengthening economic and commercial relations with Beijing represents an important element for the growth of their economies (Hasan, 2026). In this sense, the renminbi appears as an unofficial strategic element of the bloc to reduce dependence on the dollar.

Within this process, it is possible to identify four main strategies of Chinese foreign policy aimed at promoting a reconfiguration of the monetary and financial system through the expansion of renminbi internationalization. These include: strengthening bilateral and multilateral partnerships with peripheral countries through non-Western platforms in order to diversify commercial relations, such as UnionPay and the Cross-Border Interbank Payment System (CIPS); the use of the renminbi in strategic oil and gas markets, a phenomenon known as the petroyuan, which allows China, one of the world's largest oil importers, to partially circumvent the power relationship historically established between the dollar and the global oil market; political support for the expansion of BRICS+ through

the inclusion of new members with strong participation in global value chains, particularly in the energy sector, while also strengthening trade relations with these new members; and the expansion of cooperation with the Global South, especially with countries sanctioned by the United States, through projects under the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI), with investments made in renminbi as an alternative financial mechanism for these countries.

Thus, the internationalization of the renminbi has increasingly become part of Chinese foreign policy as a strategy to adjust the International Monetary and Financial System within a context of hegemonic transition (Liu, 2025). In this scenario, the de-dollarization of regional trade promoted by the bloc represents an important platform of cooperation through which China can implement part of its national strategy focused on strengthening the renminbi. However, it is important to emphasize that neither China nor BRICS+ intends to replace the dollar in global trade, but rather to strengthen their monetary sovereignty in order to mitigate the effects of the unequal relations historically promoted by the U.S. dollar as part of American foreign policy (Lui, 2025).

Therefore, a gradual reconfiguration of power relations in the monetary field can be observed, driven by China's strategic interest in strengthening the renminbi within a broader context of hegemonic transition in the international system. The growing use of the currency in transactions among BRICS+ countries not only provides an alternative to the dollar, but also demonstrates China's increasing capacity to structure economic mechanisms parallel to the traditional monetary order. In this sense, the de-dollarization agenda within the bloc partly reflects and reinforces China's political strategy of renminbi internationalization.

Conclusion

Considering that currency represents a space of conflict in interstate relations within the dynamics of capitalism, the BRICS+ de-dollarization project reflects a political decision that questions the current configuration of the international monetary field. Since BRICS+ represents a platform of cooperation aimed at reforming the International Monetary and Financial System, without necessarily proposing a rupture or systemic transformation, the competitive dynamic between currencies remains present in the debate surrounding the de-dollarization process.

In this sense, the research assumes that currency operates within a political space in which the structure of the international monetary system is shaped by historically constructed power relations among states, as well as by their economic and strategic interests expressed through foreign policy. These dynamics influence the relations of dependence and the degree of autonomy of national economies. Based on this perspective, the research finds that the de-dollarization process does not occur uniformly within the bloc, as it reflects different national interests and internal disputes.

Within this process, China emerges as a central actor in shaping the debate on de-dollarization within BRICS+. By articulating its national strategic interests, Beijing uses the bloc as a platform for economic cooperation to pursue two simultaneous objectives: reducing dependence on the dollar in intra-bloc trade and advancing the internationalization of the renminbi. In this way, a convergence can be observed between the political project of de-dollarization promoted by the group and China's interest in expanding the international relevance of its currency.

In this context, China strengthens the role of the renminbi in the bloc's economic relations through several instruments, such as the creation of its own payment systems, the expansion of economic partnerships with countries of the Global South, the institutional expansion of BRICS+, and the promotion of the currency in strategic markets for the global economy. The growing use of the renminbi in intra-bloc transactions therefore reflects a political strategy aimed at expanding China's monetary influence. However, the reduction of the dollar's centrality does not necessarily mean the end of asymmetries within the international monetary system; rather, it may only partially shift the axis of monetary power from Washington to the economic relations among the bloc's countries.

Bibliographical References

COHEN, Benjamin J. *A geografia do dinheiro*. São Paulo: UNESP, 2014.

FIORI, José Luís. *Estados e moedas no desenvolvimento das nações*. Petrópolis: Vozes, 2012.

GÜRCAN, Efe Can. *Multipolarization, south-south cooperation and the rise of post-hegemonic governance*. London: Routledge, 2019.

HASAN, Md Ali. *The BRICS Challenge to the US Dollar*. 2026. Thesis (Doctorate) – Masaryk University, Faculty of Social Studies, Brno, 2026.

LIU, Zongyuan Zoe. *China's De-dollarisation Initiatives: Strategies and Constraints*. Rome: Istituto Affari Internazionali (IAI), 2025.

METRI, Mauricio. *História e diplomacia monetária*. São Paulo: Dialética, 2023.

STRANGE, Susan. *Dinheiro insano: quando as regras do jogo financeiro são defeituosas*. Tradução de Sérgio Bath. Rio de Janeiro: Record, 1998.

TAVARES, Maria da Conceição; FIORI, José Luís (orgs.). *Poder e dinheiro: uma economia política da globalização*. Petrópolis: Vozes, 1998.

TAYLOR, Monique. *Challenging dollar dominance? The geopolitical dimensions of renminbi (RMB) internationalisation*. *Journal of Current Chinese Affairs*, v. 54, n. 3, p. 430-447, 2025.